

EFFECT OF SEAWATER ABSORPTION ON THE EXPLOSIVE BLAST RESISTANCE OF CARBON FIBRE LAMINATE

Alex Gargano¹, Khomkrit Pingkarawat², Vanessa Pickerd³, Raj Das⁴, Adrian P. Mouritz⁵

¹ 124 Latrobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia, 3000, Sir Lawrence Wackett Aerospace Research Centre, School of Engineering, RMIT University, s3332790@student.rmit.edu.au, www.rmit.edu.au

² 124 Latrobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia, 3000, Sir Lawrence Wackett Aerospace Research Centre, School of Engineering, RMIT University, khomkrit.pingkarawat@rmit.edu.au, www.rmit.edu.au

³ 506 Lorimer Street, Port Melbourne, Australia, 3207, Maritime Division, Defence Science & Technology Group, Vanessa.Pickerd@dsto.defence.gov.au, www.dst.defence.gov.au

⁴ 124 Latrobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia, 3000, Sir Lawrence Wackett Aerospace Research Centre, School of Engineering, RMIT University, raj.das@rmit.edu.au, www.rmit.edu.au

⁵ 124 Latrobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia, 3000, Sir Lawrence Wackett Aerospace Research Centre, School of Engineering, RMIT University, adrian.mouritz@rmit.edu.au, www.rmit.edu.au

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ABSTRACT

The influence of seawater absorption on the explosive blast response of a woven carbon-vinyl ester laminate is experimentally investigated by immersing the laminate in artificial seawater (2.9% salinity) at a temperature of 30°C for up to three months. The laminate was then subjected to increasing shock wave impulse loads by varying both the mass and stand-off distance of plastic explosive (PE) charges. High-speed digital image correlation (DIC) during explosive blast testing revealed significant variations in dynamic deflections for the laminate following seawater immersion, particularly at high blast impulse levels. Non-destructive evaluation of the laminate using through-transmission ultrasonics, X-ray computed tomography (CT) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed that blast induced-damage such as fibre-matrix debonding, matrix cracking, delamination and fibre rupture occurred irrespective of the amount of absorbed water. However, greater amounts of damage were observed in the seawater saturated panels, most notably for the low blast impulses. This was due to softening and weakening of the polymer matrix and the fibre-matrix interface by the absorbed water.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced polymer composites are used in a wide variety of naval vessels and ship structures, such as superstructures, masts, helicopter hangers, rudders and propellers [1, 2]. Composites offer many advantages over conventional ship materials (e.g., steel and aluminium), and include, reduced topside weight (for improved sea-keeping, range and fuel economy); superior corrosion resistance; lower radar cross-section for improved stealth; and weak magnetic properties for reduced likelihood of detonation of magnetic sea-mines.

Despite the benefits of using composite materials in naval ship structures, a long-standing concern is the loss of stiffness, strength and other mechanical properties caused by water absorption, when wear of the protective gel coating occurs. Naval ship components situated below the water-line such as the hull section can absorb water directly from the sea, whereas composites above the water-line absorb water from sea-spray, mist, rain and other sources. A potential problem with absorption of water by composite materials (particularly as chemically-bound water) is the possibility of softening and damage to the polymer matrix and fibre-matrix interface [3, 4]. The effect of seawater absorption on the mechanical properties is complex; for many composite materials their strength and stiffness are degraded under tensile, flexural, compressive and interlaminar shear loads [5-8]. However,

improvements can occur to some properties, for example impact damage resistance, due to plasticisation of the polymer matrix leading to an increase in toughness and ductility [9, 10]. Therefore, it is unclear whether water absorption by composites will improve or degrade their damage resistance against explosive blasts. While the response of composites to explosive blast loads have been extensively studied [11-15], the studies have been performed on ‘dry’ materials which have not been exposed to water or moist environmental conditions.

The aim of the study presented in this paper is to experimentally determine the effect of absorbed water on the explosive blast response of a composite laminate. The material was a woven carbon fibre-vinyl ester laminate, which is used in some naval ship structures. The laminate was submerged in artificial seawater for increasing periods of time, and then its deformation and damage responses when impulsively loaded by the air shock wave generated by an explosive charge was determined. The results presented in this paper provide new insights into the effect of absorbed water on the response of composite materials to explosive blast loads.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Composite Materials

The carbon fabric used in the laminate was single ply plain woven fabric (50:50 ratio of warp and weft tows) with continuous carbon rovings (12K) at an areal density of 600 g/m². The carbon fabric was stacked into preforms with the warp tows aligned in the same direction, producing a cross-ply stacking [0/90] pattern. The laminate was infused with liquid vinyl ester resin (SPV 1265 supplied by Nuplex Composites) at room temperature using the vacuum bagging resin infusion (VBRI) process. Before infusion, the vinyl ester was catalysed using 0.8 wt% MEKP solution (40 wt% MEKP in dimethyl phthalate) (Norox from Nuplex Composites). Following the VBRI process, the laminate was allowed to gel and partially cure at 20°C for 24 hours, and was then post-cured at 80°C for one hour. The laminate panels were 4.2±0.1 mm thick and had a fibre volume content of 50±4%. It is noted that the fibre-matrix interfacial bond strength is low for this material system, with an interfacial shear failure stress of 22±2 MPa.

2.2 Seawater Durability Testing

Composite panels were fully immersed in artificial seawater with a salinity content of around 2.9% and temperature of 30±1 °C for up to three months. The panels were withdrawn from the seawater at regular intervals to measure the mass gain due to water absorption. The panels were wiped dry using a lint-free towel to remove surface moisture, and then weighed within an accuracy of 0.1 mg to monitor the mass change. The percentage mass change of the composite panel (M) was calculated by the expression:

$$M = \frac{M_i - M_0}{M_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where M_i is the mass of the panel after a given seawater immersion time and M_0 is the original mass. Panels were withdrawn at one month and three months, representing full and beyond saturation conditions, respectively. The effect of immersion time on the percentage mass change of the carbon/vinyl ester composite is shown in Figure 1. The composite rapidly absorbed water over an initial ~400 hours of immersion time and then reached a steady-state (plateau) weight gain, and this behaviour is indicative of Fickian-type diffusion of water into the composite.

Figure 1: Seawater uptake with time for carbon-fibre vinyl ester laminate.

2.3 Explosive Blast Testing

The lay-out of the experimental facility used for explosive testing of the laminate is shown in Figure 2. The facility consists of an enclosed steel plate-lined concrete chamber fitted with viewing windows to observe the explosion and the dynamic deformation of the composite target. The targets were flat 275 × 275 mm square laminate panels held within a steel window frame having a 250 × 250 mm aperture. The frame was internally lined with soft rubber in contact with the edge of the panel which allowed the laminate to undergo out-of-plane bending freely under the pressure exerted by the shock wave without causing edge clamping damage; a common problem in explosive blast testing of flat panels [15].

Figure 2: Explosive blast experimental set-up.

The shock wave was generated using a spherical plastic explosive Type 4 (PE4) charge made of RDX (cyclotrimethylenetrinitramine). The explosive was fired using a 3.8 g RP-80 EWB electric detonator. The overpressure-time responses of the incident and reflected shock waves were measured

using two free-field pressure transducers (Kulite XTL-190). By increasing the charge mass (from 100 to 160g) or reducing the stand-off distance (distance from charge to target) from 1.0 m to 0.4 m, it was possible to controllably increase the peak overpressure and impulse of the blast wave, as given in Table 1. Panels were exposed to both near- and far-field explosive tests. The near-field being when the panel is loaded by the primary shock wave as well as the trailing detonation products and the far-field condition being when the stand-off distance exceeds the size of the fireball.

Explosive weight (g)	Stand-off distance (m)	Peak blast wave pressure (MPa)	Blast wave impulse (Pa.s)	Field condition
100	0.8	1.30	154	Far
100	0.6	3.36	219	Far
100	0.4	10.9	353	Near
160	0.4	16.0	463	Near

Table 1: Conditions used for the explosive blast testing.

The experiments were recorded using three Photon high-speed cameras (one FASTCAM SA-X, two FASTCAM SA-5). The fire-ball generated by the explosive, including its interaction with the laminate was filmed using the Photron SAX high-speed photography camera operated at a frame rate of 30000 s⁻¹. The two Photron SA5 cameras were positioned behind the target, at a distance of 1.7 m and angle of 22.5° from the centre of the panel. Prior to testing, the back surface of the laminate targets was painted white and then speckled with black dots to perform high-speed digital image correlation (DIC) during the impulse loading event. The DIC system used in this study was ARAMIS (GOM GmbH), and was used to measure the out-of-plane deflections and strains of the laminate targets.

2.4 Non-Destructive Evaluation

The laminate was non-destructively inspected before and after blast testing using through-transmission ultrasonic scanning, X-ray computed tomography and scanning electron microscopy. The ultrasonics scanning was performed in a water bath using UTwin software (Mistras Group Inc.) operated with two 2.25 MHz transducers. The X-ray computed tomography was performed using a GE Phoenix v/tome/xs X-ray CT unit with a micro-focus X-ray tube operated at a voltage of 50 kV and a current of 235 mA.

2.5 Mechanical Property Testing

Flexural and interlaminar shear properties of the laminate were determined for different immersion times using a minimum of four samples for each condition. The flexural properties were measured using the three-point bend test with a support span-to-thickness ratio of 16-to-1 in accordance with ASTM D7264/D7264M [16]. The flexural coupons were 150 mm long and 25.5 mm wide, and the warp tows were aligned perpendicular to the load pin. The coupons were loaded to failure at a maximum deflection rate of 1 mm/min. The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) was measured using the short beam shear test method according to ASTM D2344/D2344M [17]. The samples were 24 mm long and 8 mm wide, and the support span was set to 16 mm. The coupons were loaded at a cross-head displacement rate of 1 mm/min until either the load dropped by 30%, two-piece specimen failure occurred or the cross-head displacement exceeded the specimen thickness. The measured flexural and interlaminar shear strength properties for the different seawater immersion times are given in Table 2. The full and beyond saturation conditions refer to 1 and 3 months immersed in the seawater, respectively.

Seawater immersion condition	Dry	Full saturation	Beyond saturation
Flexural modulus (GPa)	36.4 (±3.38)	31.5 (±0.89)	28.6 (±1.55)
Flexural strength	230 (±21.7)	211 (±3.54)	181 (±11.3)

(MPa)			
Flexural failure strain	0.93 (± 0.08)	1.12 (± 0.04)	1.17 (± 0.09)
(%)			
Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	29.4 (± 1.28)	20.3 (± 0.85)	18.9 (± 1.06)

Table 2: Flexural and interlaminar shear properties of carbon fibre vinyl ester laminate.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The flexural and interlaminar shear properties of the laminate decreased with increasing time immersed in the seawater. The flexural strength and modulus decreased respectively by 14% and 8% after one month immersion. After three months, the flexural strength and modulus both reduced by ~20%, demonstrating further softening and weakening of the laminate beyond saturation. This trend was also measured for the interlaminar shear strength; an initial 31% decrease after one month followed by a total reduction of 36% after three months. A reduction to the interlaminar shear strength is indicative of weakening of the fibre-matrix interface due to the absorbed water.

The deformation response of the laminate when blast loaded was measured using the high-speed DIC technique. Figure 3 shows the centre-point deflection versus time profiles of the laminate targets in the dry, full and beyond saturation conditions for low and high intensity blast test conditions. The maximum deflections for the dry and fully-saturated laminate were similar when dynamically loaded with the low intensity blast (~150Pa.s), whereas the beyond saturation laminate deflected ~15% more. It was expected that both the full and beyond saturation laminate would deflect more than the dry laminate considering the degradation to the flexural stiffness. The reason for the better flexural rigidity retention of the full saturation laminate under blast loading at this stage is not clear. However, at a high intensity blast (~350 Pa.s), the maximum centre-point deflection was greater for the full and beyond saturated laminates, and this is attributed to the significantly softening and weakening caused by the absorbed water.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Centre-point displacement vs post-detonation time curves for the laminates subjected to (a) low intensity (154 Pa.s) and (b) high intensity (353 Pa.s) explosive blasts.

The effect of increasing blast impulse loading on the maximum centre-point displacement for the laminates in the dry, saturated and beyond saturated conditions is shown in Figure 4. The deformation experienced by the laminate was similar at the low shock wave impulses (≤ 300 Pa.s); however the beyond saturation conditioned panel deflected $\sim 10\%$ more. When the blast impulse exceeded ~ 300 Pa.s, the full and beyond saturation conditioned laminates deflected between 20-30% more than the dry panel. This is most likely due to the softening of the laminate from seawater ingress.

Figure 4: Effect of blast impulse on the maximum centre-point displacement of the laminates for the different seawater absorption conditions.

After blast testing, the dry and seawater conditioned laminates were examined using through-transmission ultrasonic scanning to determine the amount of damage. Through-transmission (C-scan) images of the entire laminate revealed delamination damage caused by the blast wave, quantified as a

percentage area. Examples of C-scan images of the laminate pre-blast and post-blast are given in Figure 5. The images are presented on a scale where red corresponds to a strong receiving ultrasonic signal and blue relates to complete attenuation of ultrasonic signal. Complete attenuation of the ultrasonic signal is directly correlated to a damaged area due to the formation of delamination cracks.

Figure 5: Example ultrasonic C-scan images taken (a) pre-blast and (b) post-blast (219 Pa.s impulse) revealing delamination caused by the blast.

At the low blast impulse (~ 150 Pa.s), the percentage damage area is $\sim 50\%$, $\sim 65\%$ and $\sim 80\%$ for the dry, full saturation and beyond saturation conditions, respectively. The greater percentage damage area for the seawater immersed panels is due to the continual material degradation up to and beyond full saturation. This same trend was also seen for the ~ 220 Pa.s blast, where the percentage area of the laminate that had delamination damage was $\sim 75\%$, $\sim 90\%$ and $\sim 95\%$ for the dry, full saturation and beyond saturation conditions, respectively. However, at the higher blast impulse (~ 450 Pa.s), all panels exhibit complete delamination over the entire panel area, irrespective of seawater saturation condition.

Figure 6: Effect of increasing blast impulse on the percentage area of the laminate targets that contain delamination cracks.

X-ray computed tomography was used to identify the types of blast-induced damage suffered by the laminate. Damage types such as fibre-matrix debonding, transverse inter-tow cracking and matrix

cracking in the resin-rich regions was found for a low shock wave impulse as seen in Figure 7, whereas delamination and through-thickness rupture were observed at the high blast wave impulses.

Figure 7: Blast induced damage (a) inter-tow cracking and (b) interfacial debonding after a low intensity shock blast (154 Pa.s)

4 CONCLUSION

The present study has demonstrated that the absorption of seawater into a carbon fibre-vinyl ester laminate results in a greater amount of damage caused by explosive blast loading. When blast loaded, the laminate, irrespective of the amount of absorbed water, experienced fibre-matrix interfacial cracking, matrix cracking and inter-tow cracking, and (at high blast intensity) fibre/tow fracture and delamination. However, at the ~150 Pa.s and ~220 Pa.s blast impulse, the amount of interfacial and inter-tow cracking increases with immersion time (from zero to one month to three months) and subsequent saturation level resulting in a greater overall damage in the laminate.

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